

**STUDY OF THE PROCESSES OF BIOCHEMICAL ACTION OF THE
COORDINATION COMPOUND OF COBALT II-NITRATE AND
QUINAZOLINE-4-ONN WITH 3-INDOLE FATTY ACID ON THE
VARIETY "MORUS ALBA" OF THE PLANT MORACEAE.**

¹Tadjiboyeva Moxidil Zafar qizi

¹Madiraximova Muazzam Qahramon qizi

¹Ismoilova Ozoda Otabek qizi

¹Axmedjanova Lutfinso Daniyar qizi

²Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich

¹Student Tashkent State Agrarian University

²Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7772898>

Annotation: The article provides methods for the development of the root system in the presence of various solvents, the development of the processes of biochemical action on the variety "morus alba" of the mulberry plant moraceae, the reaction of its action with indole lactic acid and the synthesis of the coordination compound of the resulting compound with cobalt (II)-nitrate.

Key words: Quinazoline-4-on, indole lactic acid, reaction, cobalt (II) - nitrate, coordination compound, Moraceae plant, morus alba, variety, biochemical effect, solvent, root system, development, leaf, photosynthesis, fruit, increased carbohydrate content, nutrients, harotate, moisture, soil composition.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the fact that the root of the mulberry tree is very well developed, this plant is very demanding on nutrients, temperature, moisture, soil composition.

So, despite the well-developed root system of the mulberry tree, in order to increase the amount of carbon contained in the abundant and high-quality leaf mass and fruit, mulberry groves should be established on fruitful, soft soil lands. Most of the lands of Central Asia consist of sandy and loamy soils (Karakum, Kyzylkum, Karshi deserts), which are well permeable to water, heat and air, but retain moisture and nutrients. The main reason for this is that the amount of humus in the soil is very small, that is, around 0.2-0.5%, and the thickness of the humus layer does not exceed several centimeters. Therefore, mulberry trees grow very poorly in such soils [1-3].

Applying measures such as timely tillage and proper irrigation are important in increasing soil fertility, so the inter-row and seeding of jute trees, and It is necessary to plow the lands where the chat is planted in the fall, to harrow and thresh as soon as the soil matures, and it should also be said that the soil's fertility can be destroyed and even swamped by over-watering. In order to prevent such a situation from happening, it is necessary to irrigate the bushes.

If we compare the reproduction of mulberry bushes by seeds and vegetatively in order to increase the productivity, we can be sure that the increase in productivity in the first case is different in different environments. While it is possible to observe a very slow growth of leaf yield in bush mulberries grown from seedlings, in bush mulberries that have their own roots, the yield increases sharply in the second year of leaf use, in other words, the yield in the first year is higher than the yield in the second year. It was observed that it increased by almost 40%. In bush mulberry orchards with arrow roots, when the row spacing is 3 meters, the number of mulberry bushes per hectare is 3,700, and the number of mulberry bushes per hectare is 3 meters. leaf yield was 2.8-3.0 tons per head, 10-12 tons in the second year, and 13-14 tons in the third year. It can be seen that in the third year of using the mulberry tree, the mass of leaves obtained from mulberry trees was 2-3 tons more than in the first year, in the fourth year, in the mulberry trees planted from seeds, it was observed that the mass of the leaves was 2-3 tons more than the previous harvest. 0 - 2.5 times higher yield is evidenced [4-12].

Continuing the scientific work in this field, information is given on the development of the root system, the process of photosynthesis in the leaves, the methods of increasing the amount of carbohydrates in the fruit, and the processes of biochemical action of the coordination compound synthesized in the variety "morus alba" of the mulberry moraceae plant in the presence of different concentration solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL PART.

Synthesis of quinazolin-4-one.

0.2 mol of anthranilic acid and 0.2 mol of formamide are placed in a round-bottomed flask.

The reaction mixture was heated at 150°C under reflux for 1 h in Wood's alloy, and then the resulting mixture was cooled to room temperature. When placed in cold water, white crystals are formed, then filtered, dried, recrystallized in alcohol.

The reaction takes place in the following sequence:

The effect of quinazolin-4-one with 3-indolyl butyric acid.

In order to carry out biochemical processes of *Morus alba* varieties of Moraceae plant, the coordination compound formed by Cobalt (II)-nitrate and quinazolin-4-one with 3-indole butyric acid was dissolved in absolute ethyl alcohol to prevent it from dissociating into ions. prepared, then 200 milliliters of 5% and 200 milliliters of 10% solutions were prepared.

The results obtained from the conducted experiments are as follows.

1. 5% and 10% solutions of the II product in distilled water were prepared as a result of the experiment.
2. The roots of 4 Moraceae plants "*Morus alba*" one-year plant variety were soaked in 5% solution for 5 hours.
3. The roots of 4 Moraceae plant varieties "*Morus alba*" were soaked in a 10% solution for 5 hours, and the roots of one Moraceae plant "*Morus alba*" were soaked in ordinary tap water. soaked in water for 5 hours

The effect of the obtained coordination compound of cobalt (II)-nitrate and quinazolin-4-one with 3-indole butyric acid on root growth was studied.

One-year *Morus alba* species of Moraceae plant were transplanted into pots (9 pots in total) and watered every morning at 8:00 AM.

The leaf formation of Moraceae plant rooted in 10% solution for 5 hours was faster than that of annual plant variety "*Morus alba*" in 5 hours, and the length of the stem in the plants was realized in the same order.

It can be concluded that the growth rate of the root is more appropriate if the roots are planted in a 10% solution for 5 hours compared to a 5% solution.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, this complex organic compound plays an important role in hemopoiesis processes. In plants, cobalt is a necessary trace element for assimilation of molecular nitrogen, it helps the formation of nodule bacteria in the root system of legumes.

Cobalamin, known as vitamin B₁₂, is well soluble in water, vitamin-related metabolism is of great importance in biochemical processes in every cell of human, animal, plant body.

"B" group vitamins are the largest and structurally most complex vitamins. Cyanocobalamin and hydroxocobalamin are used to prevent or treat vitamin deficiencies. After assimilation into the body, they turn into adenosylcobalamin and methylcobalamin, these compounds are important in metabolic processes. All forms of group "B" vitamins are biochemically complex macrocyclic compounds containing microelements, among these vitamins, the central atom in vitamin B₁₂ is a cobalt (II)-valent cation, and it regulates metabolic processes.

References:

1. Abdullaev U. "Tutchilik". "Mehnat", T. 1991.
2. Ulfat o'g'li O. A. et al. Biological Activity of the Coordinating Compound of Quinazolin-4-One with Nickel-(II) Nitrate Hexahydrate //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 13. – С. 61-63.
3. Sapaev B., Saitkulov F. CHROMATO MASS SPECTROMETRIC ANALYSIS USING ESSENTIAL OILS //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 123-126.
4. Kholmiraev M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. DETERMINATION OF SIMPLE ESTERS IN MINT BY THE METHOD OF CHROMATOMASS SPECTROSCOPY //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 70-72.
5. Kholmiraev M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. SPECTRAL CHARACTER OF THE SIMPLE OF ETHERS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 204-206.
6. Tilyabov M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. CHROMATO MASS SPECTROMETRIC ANALYSIS USING MINT ESSENTIAL OILS //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 57-60.
7. Tilyabov M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY AND ITS ANALYTICAL CAPABILITIES //Development and innovations in science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 118-121.
8. Tilyabov M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. THE STUDY OF ESTERS CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY OF ABSOLUTE ETHANOL EXTRACT OF THE CENTRAL ASIAN MINT PLANT (LAMIACEAE) //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 61-65.
9. Kholmiraev M., Khaydarov G., Saitkulov F. METHOD OF OBTAINING HERBAL MINT EXTRACT //International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 66-69.
10. Saitkulov F. et al. STUDYING THE PROPERTIES OF THE UV SPECTRA OF QUINAZOLIN-4-ONES AND-TIONS //Development and innovations in science. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 24-27.
11. Saitkulov F. et al. STUDY OF THE STRUCTURE OF 2, 3-DIMETHYLQUINAZOLINE-4-ON //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 5-10.
12. Сaitкулов Ф. Э., Элмуратов Б. Ж., Гиясов К. АЛКИЛИРОВАНИЯ ХИНАЗОЛИН-4-ОНА «МЯГКИМ» И «ЖЕСТКИМ» АЛКИЛИРУЮЩИМИ АГЕНТАМИ //Universum: химия и биология. – 2023. – №. 1-2 (103). – С. 53-56.

13. Murodillayevich K. M., Shoyimovich K. G., Ergashevich S. F. Studying the Aroma of Mint Essential Oil //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 54-56.

14. Baymuratova G. O., Nasimov K. M. THE COORDINATION COMPOUND OF COBALT CHLORIDE WITH 6-BENZYLAMINOPURINE AND AN EXPLANATION OF ITS BIOLOGII ACTIVITY //Kimyo va tibbiyot: nazariyadan amaliyotgacha. – 2022. – C. 60-62.

15. Baymuratova G. O., Nasimov K. M. THE COORDINATION COMPOUND OF COBALT CHLORIDE WITH 6-BENZYLAMINOPURINE AND AN EXPLANATION OF ITS BIOLOGII ACTIVITY //Kimyo va tibbiyot: nazariyadan amaliyotgacha. – 2022. – C. 60-62.

16. Murodovich N. H. et al. PREPARATION AND STRUCTURE OF 6-BENZYLAMINOPURINE //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 9. – №. 12. – C. 724-726.

